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Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Imaging of ocean and ice phenomena

1995 - 1998

Final Report

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Norwegian Research Council
(NT)
Project no. 107628/420**

by

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Project Summary

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data from satellites are used increasingly for earth observation and particularly for studies and monitoring of the marine environment. It is data from the European Space Agency's ERS programme which has triggered this development. Since 1991 the ERS-1 and -2 satellites have provided the research community with large amounts of SAR images with about 20 m resolution and in 100 km wide swaths. Norwegian scientists who need SAR data are in a favourable position because Tromsø Satellite Station has been built up to an excellent facility for downloading, processing and distribution of SAR data in near real time. The station delivers SAR data for Northern Europe and large parts of the Arctic.

Through demonstration projects funded by the Norwegian Space Centre, the European Commission and the European Space Agency it has been possible to identify a number of applications for SAR within environmental research and monitoring. Through the SAR strategy programme it has been possible to carry out basic research in some of these applications, addressing surface waves, surface winds, waves, surface slicks, eddies fronts and sea ice. The research tasks have been focused on algorithm development for SAR wind retrieval in coastal and ice edge regions, studies of wave breaking by SAR, ocean fronts and eddies, detection of oil spill and natural films, and investigations of sea ice processes and phenomena. Field validation of results obtained with SAR data has been an important element in the SAR strategy programme.

Through the SAR strategy programme the Nansen Center has built up its expertise to an international level in detection and monitoring ocean and ice features by SAR. Spin-off effects have been projects supported by ESA, EU and oil companies where SAR products and services have been used such as wind monitoring, oil spill and slick monitoring, detection of natural oil seeps, mapping of eddies and fronts and operational ice monitoring. Further refinement of SAR algorithms, processing and interpretation techniques, and integration with other types of remote sensing and field data as well as numerical model results is required in order to produce viable products which can be offered to potential users in a commercial or operational context.

1. Background and justification

The importance of the coastal zone as an area of intense human activity with consequent environmental impact is beginning to be recognized. An important pre-requisite for the sustainable management of coastal resources is the capability to predict change in coastal areas over periods of one to several decades. This requires an upscaling of the level of coastal marine research, and in particular, the strengthening of the technology and infrastructure for large scale and long term observation of the coastal seas. In polar regions, the presence of sea ice has severe impact on human activities, especially on sea transportation. Coastal monitoring systems for polar regions therefore need to include observation of sea ice as one of their modules. Sea ice is also important to monitor because it is a sensitive parameter to climate variability (Johannessen et al., 1996 b).

Recognition of the importance of the coastal zone has led to the establishment of the international programme Land Ocean Interaction in Coastal Zones (LOICZ) within the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP). A coastal zone module for monitoring the coastal zone environment and its changes is also an integral component of the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), which was established in 1993 by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC), the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the International Council for Scientific Unions (ICSU). The task is to design and implement a scientifically based system of coastal observations and predictions to fulfill economic, social, environmental, and scientific objectives. This module has a high priority to many coastal states because of the importance of the coastal area for development and the intimate effects of coastal changes on economic development and human habitation. A global and multi-disciplinary approach is prescribed and the initial emphasis will be on monitoring changes in the coastal environment. Remote sensing data and particularly SAR data will be of special significance in this phase. GOOS also has a European regional programme called EuroGOOS where the coastal zone and polar regions are among the specific projects (EuroGOOS Plan, 1997; Johannessen et al., 1997 a, b).

In the Svalbard region, a sea ice monitoring service based on SAR data is urgently needed to improve the safety for fishing vessels. In December 1995 the shrimp trawler "Atlantic Prawn" sunk because it was captured in sea ice (Pettersson et al, 1996). This accident could have been avoided with a SAR ice monitoring system in operation. In the Northern Sea Route, oil and gas transport by tankers can become an important part of the ship traffic in near future. The presence of sea ice in the region requires ice monitoring of the best possible quality to avoid accidents and enable efficient navigation. Satellite data, especially SAR data, delivered to ships in the Northern Sea Route have proven to be very important for navigation in the area (Johannessen et al., 1996, 1997b, 1998; Melentyev et al., 1997).

In addition to sea ice, there are many processes and parameters which are important in the context of navigational and environmental safety, such as wind, waves, currents, bathymetry, ocean colour, turbidity, movement of algal blooms, and transport of oil spills and other pollutants. Conventional instruments to measure these parameters can be located only at discrete locations and are not likely to provide the spatial coverage necessary for coastal management applications. Remote sensing with sensors of today and the near future offers these possibilities if proper services are implemented. The technology is here today.

2. Objectives

The overall objective of the SAR strategy programme is to advance the physical understanding of SAR imaging mechanisms to improve the monitoring and forecasting of processes in the ocean-atmospheric boundary layer by better interpretation and quantification of wind, waves, slicks, eddies and fronts and sea ice characteristics.

3. Dr. Scient. scholarships

Four Dr. Scient scholarships have been supported by the SAR strategy programme:

Birgitte Rugaard Furevik: Wind in the marginal ice zone (scheduled to be completed at the end of 2000)

Erik Korsbakken: SAR wind algorithm development (employed as scientist at Norwegian Defence Research Establishment from 01.05.1998)

Jostein A. Solhaug: SAR interaction with sea ice (interrupted May 1999)

Heidi Espedal: SAR slick detection and classification (completed in July 1998)

4. Overview of project results

4.1 SAR wind in ocean and coastal regions

A new SAR wind algorithm has been developed by Dr. Scient. candidate Erik Korsbakken (Korsbakken et al., 1998) which extracts both wind speed and direction. This algorithm provides high resolution wind fields which are more accurate than the wind field from weather forecasting models. The COASTWATCH experiment 1995 provided valuable in situ data for validation of the wind algorithm (Johannessen et al., 1997c). Wind retrieval from SAR will become very important from 2000, because ENVISAT will carry SAR (which provide wind fields over 500 km swaths), but no wind scatterometer. SAR derived wind field can be used in operational weather forecasting, particularly in coastal regions and in the marginal ice zone, but is yet not implemented. The Nansen Center has also suggested to use this method to make detailed wind energy maps for coastal regions to be used in planning of wind mills along the Norwegian coast as well as abroad (Johannessen et al., 1998).

4.2 SAR Wind observations in the marginal ice zone

Dr. Scient candidate Birgitte Furevik is investigating the possibility to use SAR for extraction of high resolution wind fields in ice edge regions where no other observation method exist. The first results of comparison between SAR and Scatterometer data in the Greenland Sea are published by

Furevik and Korsbakken (1998) and recently presented at the remote sensing Conference in Tromsø (8 - 12 June 1998). The wind in the ice edge region is highly variable and often different from winds in open ocean or in the interior of the ice. Improved wind data in the ice edge region will be very important for better weather and ice forecasting as well as for all kind of ships and marine operations in polar regions.

4.3 SAR ice classification and interpretation

Dr. Scient candidate Jostein Solhaug is investigating the SAR ice imaging mechanisms, combining theoretical studies and field observations in the Svalbard region. The results of his work will be used to improve ice classification algorithms and adopt them for use with different SAR systems such as ERS, RADARSAT and ENVISAT. The first results of ice observation and ice classification by RADARSAT in the Northern Sea Route are presented at IGARSS'98 in Seattle, 6 - 10 July (Sandven et al., 1998). SAR ice interpretation and classification results presented in a SAR ice catalogue (Johannessen et al., 1997 c) are used in remote sensing education which Nansen Center scientists perform at several universities and colleges in Norway/Svalbard. Jostein Solhaug has given lectures at UNIS, Svalbard and Høgskolen in Bergen.

4.4 SAR surface film and oil slicks

Heidi Espedal completed her Dr. Scient.thesis (1. July 1998) on SAR detection of oil spill and natural film in coastal regions with support from the SAR strategy programme and a personal scholarship from the Norwegian Research Council. The thesis consists of five papers (Espedal, 1996, 1998a,b,c,d) and some of the results have been used in development of the Norwegian SAR oil spill detection system which is run operationally by Tromsø Satellite Station (Hamre et al., 1997, Espedal et al., 1997).

5. Field experiments

5.1 COASTWATCH'95

The COASTWATCH ERS 1/2 Tandem experiment in September 1995 with R/V Håkon Mosby off the southwest coast of Norway, funded by the SAR strategy programme, was used to collect in situ data for validation of SAR-derived parameters on wind, coastal currents, fronts and slick. The results of the experiment are published by Johannessen et al. (1997c, 1998) and Korsbakken et al. (1998). The COASTWATCH experiment was essential for documentation of SAR ocean features and rates among the best SAR coastal experiments ever carried out.

5.2 ICEWATCH

The Nansen Center was selected by ESA to be the project leader of the ICEWATCH project (Johannessen et al., 1997b), where the objective was to demonstrate real-time sea ice monitoring in the Northern Sea Route using satellite radar technology. ICEWATCH is the first joint project in

earth observation between ESA and the Russian Space Agency. One of the tasks was to organize field expeditions with icebreakers from Murmansk Shipping Company where SAR data were transmitted in near real-time to the vessel. Ice scientists from the Nansen Center in St. Petersburg were also involved both in the field experiment and in analysis of the SAR data. The results of the project have shown that SAR data in near real time offers a unique new possibility to improve the ice mapping which is needed in ice navigation (Johannessen et al., 1997 b, e; Sandven et al., 1998). The field experiments in the Northern Sea Route supplied the SAR strategy programme with invaluable in situ data for our SAR ice classification algorithm development and validation.

6. Specific results

6.1 SAR wind retrieval

In a paper published in Journal of Geophysical Research (Vol. 103, No. C4, pages 7857 - 7874, April 1998) Korsbakken et al. carried out a systematic analysis of the mesoscale coastal wind field conditions expressed in a series of ERS-1 and -2 SAR images obtained off the southern coast of Norway during the COASTWATCH'95 experiment. Quantitative estimates of wind speed and direction are based on examination of both the SAR image backscatter characteristics and the spectral properties. Two different wind retrieval models have been used: SWA and CMOD4. The same algorithms are used for wind studies in the Greenland Sea and the marginal ice zone (section 6.2).

6.2 Using SAR in the study of processes in the marginal ice zone.

The aim of the study is to enhance the use of SAR in the study of the atmospheric boundary layer and ocean mesoscale phenomena related to the marginal ice zone (MIZ). It is interesting to focus on the possibility for using SAR in extracting high resolution wind field in ice edge regions where no other observation methods exist. To do this, some points are investigated:

1. Validation of the SAR extracted wind field in general.
2. Study the spatial resolution obtainable from SAR.
3. Validation towards in situ observations in the MIZ of both the above points.

Validation of the SAR derived wind has been done towards in situ data (e.g. [Vachon and Dobson 1996], [Korsbakken et al. 1998]), but a validation of the use of CMOD IF2 on SAR data towards the WSC wind field has not been possible before the Tandem Phase of the ERS-1 and 2. In this phase the ERS-1 WSC and the ERS-2 SAR measured the same area on the sea surface north of 63° with only 30 minutes time lag. In order to address the first objective above, the extracted wind field from SAR Precision Images (PRI) was compared with Wind Scatterometer (WSC) wind field products obtained during the Tandem Phase. A total number of 36 SAR scenes in 6 passes over the Greenland Sea is available (Table 1).

Table 1 Data used in the study.

Date	ERS-1 WSC		ERS-2 SAR			Hindcast Time
	Orbit	Time	Orbit	Frame	Time	

950822	21454	1212	01767	2133, 2151, 2169, 2187, 2205, 2223, 2241, 2259	1244	1200
950825	21497	1219	01810	2223, 2241	1251	1200
950901	21597	1158	01910	2025, 2043, 2061, 2079, 2097, 2115, 2133, 2151, 2169, 2187, 2205, 2223	1228	1200
950911	21740	1144	02053	2133, 2151, 2169, 2187, 2205, 2223	1215	1200
950917	21826	1155	02139	2205, 2223, 2241	1228	1200
950927	21969	1141	02282	2187, 2205, 2223, 2241, 2259	1213	1200

The C band model used to extract the wind field in both data sets were the CMOD IF2. It is developed and used operationally on the WSC data at the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER) [Quilfen 1995]. When using this type of models on the SAR, the wind direction is needed as an input. Since this validation is done towards the WSC the wind direction from this instrument is used. Figure 1 is an example from the data set. The WSC wind field from this day reveals a strong wind front connected with a atmospheric low. 12 SAR images are available from the vicinity of the low and passes through the front. The SAR image covering the front (enhanced frame in Figure 1) is shown in Figure 2. Comparing the turning of the WSC wind vectors (white arrows) with the position of the front in the SAR image, we observe that the front has moved 20-30km during the 30 minutes.

Figure 1 Wind field in the Greenland Sea measured by the ERS-1 WSC on September 1, 1995. Sea level pressure given by the Hindcast database of the Norwegian Meteorological Institute. The frames indicate the position of SAR scenes available from this day.

Figure 2 ERS-2 SAR image covering the atmospheric front on September 1 with the WSC wind field overlaid. The white box is framing a sub-image of 25x25km. The horizontal dark band is an artifact.

Assuming that the wind field in general is stationary during the 30 minutes time lag, wind speed values extracted from the SAR can be validated towards the WSC wind field. To obtain the best possible conditions for the comparison, sub-images of 25x25km are extracted from the SAR scenes. The sub-images are centred at the WSC data wind vectors and the radar backscatter within the sub-images are averaged. Using this backscatter value as input to the CMOD IF2 together with the wind direction from the local WSC wind vector and SAR incidence angle gives the best possible conditions for the validation. In the way, wind vectors from approximately 145 WSC data points were compared with the wind speed extracted from corresponding SAR sub-images. The comparison is shown in Figure.

Figure 3 Comparison of WSC wind speed values with retrieved wind speed from SAR. Resolution of 25km is comparable with the WSC grid size. CMOD IF2 is used in retrieving both data set. Only data plotted using • are included in calculation of the linear regression line (dashed line). The points marked with × are data from the front shown in Figure 2 and points marked with o are from a front case on September 17.

In spite of the time lag it is seen from the figure that the correlation is very good. Only in the front cases there is some scatter in the comparison. This has been found to be due to moving of the border between high and low wind areas during the 30 minutes time lag. These data points (× and o) are not included in the statistics.

It is observed from Fig. Xx that the SAR is underestimating the WSC wind speed with 0.5m/s. This offset is believed to be due to a difference in incidence angles of the two sensors. If this is the case it means that the C band model used to extract the wind from SAR and WSC has to be adjusted in its dependence on the incidence angle. This subject is under investigation.

To investigate the spatial resolution obtainable from SAR, the wind field was derived in each of the SAR sub-images at a resolution of 200×200m. This gave a number of 15625 (125²) SAR wind

speed values within each sub-image. The maximum and minimum of these values is a measure of the variance in wind speed within an area in the SAR image. In Figure 4 the comparison between WSC wind vectors and the average 200m resolution SAR wind values are shown.

Figure 4 Comparison of WSC wind speed with SAR derived wind speed at a resolution of 200m.

Comparing with Fig. 3 the difference in the linear regression line is due to the non-linear conversion between backscatter and wind speed in the CMOD IF2. The larger number of data points in this plot (a total number of 290 versus 145 in Fig. Xx originates from including the points near the border of the SAR images. The dashed lines are the lines surrounding all 200m resolution data. the lines indicate a large variation in wind speed within each sub-image. This is believed to be due to the higher resolution resolving some of the turbulence in the wind field, but also reflecting an error introduced by using the same wind direction over the whole sub-image.

An example of the high resolution wind field is seen in Fig. 5 where a sub-image of 25x25km of the SAR scene in Figure 2 is shown together with the retrieved wind field for the resolutions of 1km, 500m and 200m. It is noted that the wind speed values are varying continuously over the area indicating that the spatial variation of the retrieved wind field from SAR is realistic and reflects the

atmospheric turbulence. However, it is clear that an error is made by assuming the same wind direction over this front. The error in this specific example is about -2m/s in the SAR derived wind from the low wind area. This value is estimated assuming the wind direction to be the same as further into the area on the low wind side of the front (see Figure 2).

Figure 5. SAR subimage of 25 by 25 km (a), and wind speed (b) for the subimage indicated by the colour scale.

The results derived by analysing the Tandem Phase data are useful knowledge in the further work on retrieving wind field from SAR in the MIZ.

Another wind related project evolving from the work described above, is to use the SAR and eventually the WSC wind information in combination with numerical modelling of mesoscale atmospheric phenomena, and local wind fields. A group at the Geophysical Institute, University of Bergen are working on mesoscale modelling and are interested in the information that can be provided by the spaceborne radar's. This collaboration might in time result in a wind mapping tool useful in the process of localising sites for wind mill parks along the coast.

6.3 SAR oil slicks. Heidi A. Espedals Dr. Scient work

The Dr. Scient thesis, completed in July 1998, consists of the following five papers:

6.3.1 Paper I: Oil spill and its look-alikes in ERS SAR imagery

H. A. Espedal

Earth Observation and Remote Sensing, Russian Academy of Sciences, vol. 5, pp.94-102, 1998

Objective; to analyze and describe the different oil spill look-alikes in satellite SAR imagery.

In a study of satellite SAR imaged oil spills and look-alikes caused by natural phenomena, slicks were classified according to image expression, backscatter, geographical occurrence and weather limitations. The natural phenomena identified as oil spill look-alikes included; natural film, grease ice, threshold wind speed areas, wind sheltering by land, rain cells, shear zones, internal waves and natural oil seepage. An extensive database of SAR imagery was analyzed. Each phenomenon was also discussed based on its generation mechanism and an example from ERS SAR imagery was shown.

Oil spill and its look-alikes displayed very similar backscatter values in the SAR imagery. However, rain cells, grease ice, natural oil seepage and natural film were generally found to have the sharpest edges. When classifying slicks according to geographical occurrence, weather limitations, backscatter intensity profiles, gradients and damping values, it will not give a one-to-one relationship between phenomena and their slick properties. However, to aid in the SAR image analysis, a conceptual model for a slick discrimination algorithm is suggested. Such an algorithm performs best when auxiliary data is available. This includes wind and current information, bathymetry, ship lane and platform locations and information on temperature and rain.

6.3.2 Paper II: Satellite detection of natural films on the ocean surface.

H. A. Espedal, O. M. Johannessen and J. C. Knulst

Geophysical Research Letters, vol.23, no.22, pp.3151-3154, 1996

Objective; to verify in situ that slicks in SAR imagery can be related to natural films (i.e. increased biological activity), and to improve knowledge of natural chemical-biological films under different coastal and atmospheric conditions

To study the composition of natural films and their signatures in SAR imagery, samples of the sea surface microlayer were for the first time taken simultaneously with ERS-1 SAR coverage of a study area. A remotely controlled model boat, INTERFACE I, fitted with a hydrophilic teflon drum in the front, was used to sample inside and outside slicks found in Korsfjord south-west of Bergen, Norway. The slicks seen in the SAR image were reported to the field team, and a GPS was used to navigate to the correct locations. These slicks could generally also be recognized visually, and some photographs were obtained. In addition to the surface microlayer sampling, sub-surface samples (at 50cm) were taken, and the wind was measured using an anemometer. The samples were stored, and later analyzed in a laboratory to identify the main constituents of the natural films.

The wave damping caused by the investigated slicks varied between 6 and 17dB (when compared to non slicked areas). These are values typically found for both oil and other look-alikes in satellite SAR imagery. The chemical analysis indicate an enrichment of organic constituents and a generally higher concentration of total aliphatic hydrocarbons (ALK) in the surface microlayer when a slick was present, compared to the corresponding sub-surface water. The concentration of fatty acids (FA) was generally one order of magnitude larger inside compared to outside the slicks. Thus, for the first time a relationship between natural sea surface chemistry and satellite SAR backscatter values was identified. However, the composition of each sample varied, indicating that the sea surface is of a very patch chemical nature, both for slicked and non slicked areas. Moreover, the large fatty acid molecules and particulate material observed, indicated terrestrial sources for the investigated slicks.

6.3.3. Paper III: COASTWATCH'95: ERS-1/2 SAR detection of natural film on the ocean surface.

H. A. Espedal, O. M. Johannessen, J. A. Johannessen, E. Dano, D. Lyzenga and J. Knulst
Journal of Geophysical Research, vol.103, no.C11, pp.24969-24982, 1998

Objective; to improve knowledge of natural chemical-biological films under different coastal and atmospheric conditions

To extend the documentation of natural film and its effect on satellite SAR imagery, to include different coastal and atmospheric conditions, a new slick sampling investigation was conducted during the COASTWATCH'95 tandem ERS-1/2 experiment off the south-western coast of Norway. A total of 71 satellite SAR images were obtained, 53 of these were analyzed during the field campaign. Two microlayer samplers were used, the INTERFACE I and II. The new INTERFACE II was larger (2m long) and had the teflon drum located between the catamaran floaters, and therefore performed better in open sea conditions than the INTERFACE I. It was also fitted with a GPS system, temperature probes, an anemometer and a data logger. In addition to the satellite SAR imagery, a C-band Doppler scatterometer was used to acquire shipborne radar backscatter measurements from the bow of the research vessel R/V Håkon Mosby.

Three special slick measurements are discussed in detail. For one of these verified natural films, surface drifters and the Doppler radar data showed that a convergence was responsible for the film accumulation. Another verified natural film case showed no clear convergence or shear. In the third case, no samples were obtained for chemical analysis, but a slick with finger-like extensions was investigated using the Doppler radar, and also found in the ERS-1 SAR image 6 hours later (with prevailing low winds). The slick had totally disappeared in the ERS-2 SAR image the next day. During this period the wind speed increased from 2-3m/s to 5-10m/s.

The damping caused by natural films was generally less in the SAR than in the Doppler data (both 100m resolution). This was probably due to the different incidence angles and frequencies of the instruments, thus causing a difference in Bragg wavelength.

Using a supervised slick discrimination algorithm, estimates of natural film coverage and damping were found, based on the 71 SAR images covering the experiment region. The results showed that for increasing wind speed, the percentage of film coverage in the SAR scenes expectedly decreases.

The largest film coverage (40%) was found for winds near the detection threshold (2.5m/s), while already at 5-10m/s wind the film coverage had decreased below 5% in all cases. Furthermore, increasing wind speeds also lead to decreasing damping by the natural films. The wide range of damping values, especially at low wind speeds, were believed to be due to varying film composition and thickness. Of the 71 SAR scenes, 27 were classified as containing no natural film, they all had a wind speed of 5m/s or more.

When comparing the results to the experiment conducted in 1994 in Korsfjord, the slicks investigated during COASTWATCH'95 contained smaller fatty acid molecules indicating marine organisms as their source. The fjord slicks were dominated by terrestrial sources. The COASTWATCH'95 slicks also had lower concentration of fatty acids, resulting in slightly lower damping values in the SAR imagery, 2-11dB, compared to 6-17dB for the fjord cases.

6.3.4 Paper IV: Satellite SAR oil spill detection using wind history information.

H. A. Espedal and T. Wahl

Accepted for publication in International Journal of Remote Sensing, 1998

Objective; to develop a method for use of wind history for slick age estimation in satellite SAR oil spill detection.

The North Sea is crowded with rigs and platforms engaged in the exploration of oil and natural gas. These are possible sources for oil pollution, but harmless slicks caused by e.g. run-off water, cleaning operations or wind sheltering may also be expected under certain conditions. Also, several natural phenomena may appear as dark slicks in SAR images. Therefore, further research work has been conducted on decision criteria for distinguishing true oil spills from harmless natural or man-made

slicks near North Sea installations. This work has led to some practical rules of thumb concerning the use of information about the instantaneous wind and the wind history.

Some of the natural slicks (i.e. grease ice, rain cells, internal waves and shear zones) are easily recognized based on simple weather information or due to their characteristic shape and configuration. However, when distinguishing oil spills from natural film or wind sheltering caused by oil rigs, wind information is important. Previously, SAR oil spill discrimination has been focused on instantaneous wind. If the local wind speed was more than 7m/s at the time of imaging, a slick was believed to contain oil since natural slicks will disperse at such winds, or their damping effect will disappear in the noise of wind generated waves. However, the temporal evolution of the wind (the wind history) during the day(s) before SAR imaging, may also contribute in the interpretation process. The shape of bent or angular slicks can be matched against wind history to estimate slick age. Accurate computations of slick age require detailed information of wind and surface current fields, in

addition to knowledge of viscosity and amount of slick material. However, in an operational context, it is usually sufficient to use changes in wind and currents to indicate how a slick has evolved, and thus give a rough estimate of slick age. A spill from a fixed source is assumed to move with 3% of the wind speed, and 15° to the right of the wind direction on the northern hemisphere.

This study was based on wind information only, since current data was not available. The result of including a background current, would be a slick drift vector obtained by vector-adding the current to the wind effect.

If wind is the only major factor influencing the spill shape, a linear relationship between the age of a slick, its length and the wind speed can be found (assuming a continuous release of oil from the source). The optimal situation is to have several bends on the slick, each matching a change in wind direction. Preferably, the change in wind direction should be large (e.g. from southerly to westerly winds) giving distinct bends on the slick. Simple flow charts supply a standard procedure to be followed when trying to estimate slick age. Three case studies illustrates both situations where the slick age can be estimated, and cases where wind history is not sufficient to determine slick age.

If slick age is estimated, this is used together with a new analysis of the slick signature (dB-values, texture, gradients, shape, size/length) and auxiliary data, to determine if the slick is caused by an oil spill. The proven ability of a slick to withstand certain weather conditions over a period of time, gives information about its physical characteristics, e.g. a slick that has remained connected for 24h and still gives a much darker signature than the surrounding sea, is very likely to contain oil since several studies have confirmed that natural films (dis)appear or reconfigures during periods as short as 1 day. Also, if the wind history reveals that the wind has been more than 7m/s during a period when the slick was present, it is a strong indicator of oil spill. The standard procedures described here, have been implemented operationally at Tromsø Satellite Station.

6.3.5 An ERS SAR slick discrimination algorithm

H. A. Espedal

NERSC Technical Report no. 149, 1998

Objective; to develop a standard procedure including tools, to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process.

The oil spill look-alikes in the SAR imagery have made it necessary to develop algorithms to ensure that the risk of false alarms are minimized, or preferably, eliminated. Experience has shown that the capability of the human eye (and brain) in detecting and discriminating between slicks is far beyond the reach of today's computers [Wah96]. As long as coverage is limited by interest in high priority regions, manual interpretation is feasible. However, good tools within a frame of a supervised slick discrimination algorithm, supply a standard procedure to be followed and is very useful in satellite SAR slick discrimination. Such a supervised algorithm has been developed, and it contains the following main steps;

- initial processing
- slick detection and direct analysis
- contextual analysis
- model results
- drawing a conclusion based on the combined results

The algorithm was developed based on low resolution SAR images (LRI) from Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS). The initial processing includes internal calibration (done at TSS), range normalization, linear scaling from 16 to 8 bit pixels, resampling to square 100m pixels and absolute calibration.

Methods of implementing ADC corrections for TSS LRI imagery is currently being investigated. Regular experiments are also necessary to improve absolute calibration of LRI imagery.

After initial processing, the first step of the direct analysis is to apply an edge detection filter to the SAR image. The Sobel filter rules out homogeneous imagery without edges, and is also an aid when

choosing the slicks that need further analysis. The direct analysis includes identification of possible slick sources (bright spots), shape classification, determination of dimensions and size of the slick, calculation of texture parameters, damping values and gradients. The contextual analysis makes use of

different wind (and current) data. The wind history is matched against slick shape to estimate slick age. The analysis also includes consideration of rain, temperature/season and bathymetry. Finally, information from a large data base of "hot-spots", i.e. possible spill sources, gives important input in the contextual analysis.

Testing of an oil drift model has shown the usefulness of including this as part of the slick discrimination process. Ongoing investigations are dedicated to finding a commercially available oil

drift model that is suitable for this purpose. The ERIM Ocean Model (EOM) has also been tested, and

preliminary results indicate that the model can only be used to estimate general trends in damping caused by slicks under different environmental conditions. For a slick discrimination purpose, the model should preferably be extended to allow for differences in damping effects caused by thin films and thicker oil spills.

When drawing a conclusion on slick phenomena, the direct and contextual analysis have to be considered together with the model results. This study indicates that most slicks are easy to recognize based on shape characteristics. Moreover, natural film has been identified as the look-alike most difficult to distinguish from oil spills in SAR imagery. A comparison between slick properties for oil spills and natural films showed that for natural films the drop in backscatter remained in the range 2-11dB, while for oil it was 1-16dB. The damping values for natural films seemed to drop quicker as wind speeds increased, compared to oil spills. Furthermore, the oil spills generally had a slightly more positive kurtosis than natural films. The backscatter values within a natural film slick are therefore more evenly dispersed over different values, while an oil slick is more peaked, i.e. concentrated on a few backscatter values. The gradient parameter applied here did not show the expected different trends for natural films and oil spills. Other methods of describing slick edges should therefore be investigated.

The study of SAR slicks shows, as expected, that even though some trends in slick properties have been discovered for e.g. oil spills and natural films, no one-to-one relationships are found. The supervised slick discrimination algorithm is therefore developed to standardize the procedures and make sure the same criterias are applied to all slicks in SAR images. Together with a data base containing information on typical properties of verified slick cases and the "hot-spot" data base, this will improve our ability to classify slicks.

The supervised slick discrimination algorithm was tested on 124 slicks in SAR imagery. This included 34 confirmed oil spills, 5 confirmed natural films and 5 confirmed non-oil pollutions. For the remaining cases, classification made by experienced SAR-slick scientists was used as the "correct" slick type. The two look-alikes classified as oil, were both caused by other pollution

spilled from oil platforms. The expected problem with natural films being classified as oil, was not reflected in the results. The reason is probably that "doubt" slicks are not included in the test data set. Only verified natural films or slicks previously classified as highly likely to be caused by natural film, were included. More verified natural film cases are therefore required to test the supervised slick discrimination algorithm thoroughly.

6.3.6 Main conclusions

The main objective of the thesis was:

to improve the understanding of spaceborne SAR imaging of surface slicks, and subsequently to develop a method for classification of such slicks, including oil spill and natural chemical-biological film.

Results: An extensive data base of slicks in SAR images has been developed, and two experiments have for the first time provided natural films seen in satellite SAR imagery that are verified by sampling and chemical analysis. The supervised slick classification algorithm developed here, provides a standard procedure to ensure the same criteria are applied to all slicks being investigated.

When developing the supervised algorithm, natural film was the look-alike most often difficult to distinguish from oil spills. Other pollution being spilled from oil installations or ships sometimes also caused problems.

The specific objectives and their corresponding results were:

- Objective: *to analyze and describe the different oil spill look-alikes in satellite SAR imagery.*
Results: The oil spills and look-alikes displayed similar backscatter values in SAR imagery. Rain cells, grease ice, oil (seepage) and natural film had the sharpest edges. However, no one-to-one relationship was found between phenomena and slick properties.
- Objective: *to verify in situ that slicks in SAR imagery can be related to natural films (i.e. increased biological activity).*
Results: A relationship has been found between sea surface chemistry and satellite SAR backscatter values. The concentration of fatty acids was one order of magnitude larger inside compared to outside the slicks. These slicks caused a 6-17dB damping.
- Objective: *to improve knowledge of natural chemical-biological films under different coastal and atmospheric conditions.*
Results: The major results from two experiments where natural films were studied, indicate that the coastal slicks contained smaller fatty acid molecules from marine organisms, compared to the terrestrial sources of the fjord slicks. The coastal slicks also had lower concentration of fatty acids resulting in a slightly lower damping in the SAR imagery. One verified natural film accumulation was shown to be caused by a convergence. Estimates of natural film coverage in SAR scenes revealed that the largest coverage (40%) was found for winds near detection threshold, while already at 5-10m/s winds the coverage had sunken below 5%.
- Objective: *to develop a method for use of wind history for slick age estimation in satellite SAR oil spill detection.*
Results: Several flow charts have been developed. They supply a standard procedure to be followed when using wind history in slick age estimation. The method performs best when the wind is the only major factor influencing slick shape. The slick should preferably have several

bends, each corresponding to a change in wind direction. Slick age and the proven ability of a slick to withstand certain weather conditions, will thus give information on its physical characteristics.

- Objective: *to develop a standard procedure including tools, to aid in a SAR slick discrimination process.*

Results: A supervised slick discrimination algorithm has been developed. It contains initial processing of the SAR image, slick detection and direct analysis, contextual analysis and model results. A conclusion of slick type is then based on information on typical properties of verified slicks and a "hot-spot" data base. For natural films the drop in backscatter was in the range 2-11dB, while for oil it was 1-16dB. The damping values for natural films dropped quicker as wind

speeds increased, compared to oil spills. The oil spills generally had a slightly more positive kurtosis than natural films, indicating that the backscatter values within natural film slicks are more evenly dispersed over different values, while an oil slick is more peaked (concentrated on a few backscatter values). The gradient estimates did not show any trends that were different for oil spills and natural films.

Future work

New ways of describing different slick edges should be tested. One method could be to measure the distance between the last pixel (near the a slick) containing the average non-slicked backscatter value and the first pixel containing the average slick backscatter value. This would give an indication of the "width" of the slick edge.

A new oil drift model must be chosen and implemented in the slick discrimination algorithm. This will improve the estimates of slick age, and also give a better indication of what weather conditions the slick has sustained. Ideally, this model should be able to read weather parameters directly from the files that are obtained from the Norwegian Meteorological Institute (DNMI).

The ERIM Ocean Model (EOM) should be extended to allow for damping effects of thick oil spills. Today, EOM includes the effect of surfactants on the short gravity and capillary waves by adding an extra damping term to the right-hand side of the wave action equation. It uses an empirical model for surface elasticity. Similar experiments must therefore be conducted to describe damping terms for thicker oil spills.

The hot spot data base must be updated with coordinates of the pollution sources in the Baltic Sea. This work is ongoing; the Finnish Environment Institute and the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (HELCOM) have already been contacted. The pollution control authorities in each country bordering on the Baltic Sea should also be located and addressed.

More experiments are necessary to improve our understanding of the natural film formation processes, and also to extend the number of verified slick phenomena. This is vital both for updating and testing the slick discrimination procedures.

In order to improve the absolute calibration of the satellite SAR data obtained from TSS, the ADC correction must be implemented. Moreover, regular experiments must be performed to update the calibration constant K , which then should be given in the header of each image. The algorithm should also be extended to allow analysis of ESA PRI imagery.

6.4 Frontal feature studies in the Kara Sea

The study area

The fresh water input due to river runoff into the Kara sea is about 1325 km³ per year, this is highest value among others Arctic seas. Most of this input is made by Yenisey (610 km³/year), Ob (535) and Pyasina (78) rivers. Their mouths lie so close to each other that their runoffs merge and form the one spot of fresh water. Since the sea in the estuaries neighborhood is quite shallow (20-50 m) and the outflow is so high we can expect to observe a wide range of phenomena resulted from interaction of sea and fresh waters. Thus the region should be suitable for a case study of coastal fronts.

The data set

A total of 89 ERS SAR images of open water were collected for the region for years 1994-1996. They are either in PRI (from ESA PAFs) or in LRI (from TSS) or in IMF (from NERSC) format. Only the PRI images permit the reliable calibration into NRCS units. The calibration provides for geometrical, antenna gain and ADC power loss corrections and simple speckle noise filtration. The coverage of SAR scenes is shown on figure 6. Most of the images are complimented with the weather maps. There are also six NOAA AVHRR images of 1 km resolution. The images were calibrated into degrees of brightness temperature according to NOAA specifications. Unfortunately the temporary-spatial overlapping of the SAR and AVHRR data is bad. In situ data are presented by measurements from KAREX 93,94,95 field campaigns. Each of these three expeditions data sets includes approximately 140 CTD vertical profiles, chemical, optical and meteorological measurements. Also available is digital bottom topography map with the grid spacing 6' by 3' along longitude and latitude respectively.

Figure 6. Study area for SAR ocean fronts. Each line segment is a frontal feature observed by ERS SAR.

Methodology

To get an insight into spatial consistent patterns of fronts appearing in the region all the fronts detected on the SAR images were transferred to the geographic map (Figure 6). Saying front we mean a surface phenomenon characterized by strong current velocity gradient across it. It should be noted that not only an interaction between different water masses results in such a gradient; interaction of a flow with complex bottom relief may be another reason. A front signature is considered to be the narrow, stretched image feature with positive, negative or variable radar contrast. Additional information was involved for the images interpretation if available.

Discussion

Fronts were found on 70 images among total 89. So high probability supports our initial expectations about very intensive interaction between sea and riverine water in the region. The orientation of the fronts is generally meridional. Perhaps this does not reflect the real situation because the radar is more sensitive to this kind of fronts since in this case the surface current velocity changes along the look direction. The spatial distribution of the fronts is quite random but not completely homogenous. It is more dense between 72nd and 76th meridians to the north of Ob gulf exit. This trend is not due to more frequent coverage of this region, since it persists also for year 1995 being considered solely, when the coverage was rather uniform.

The condensations of the front-like features to the west of Belyj island (A) and to the north and south of Sibiryakova island (B) are of bathymetrical origin. The water is more shallow around the islands and deepens quite sharply toward the rivers beds (for the northern B case from 3 to 20 meters). So we believe that shear fronts generates there between moving water of the rivers outflow and more calm water of the islands sandbanks. The bunch of the features in the Malygin strait (C) also results from interaction between bottom relief and current. The bottom there is not flat and tidal currents of alternating directions are as much as 3-4 knots. The front(s) along the western coast of Yamal peninsula (D) is an upwelling signature. Upwellings are known to occur in this region. Another one is visible on two of the AVHRR images as a thin strip of cold water between the shore and more warm background water (probably of Barents origin). Unfortunately the time gap between the SAR and the AVHRR images is very large.

The long front in the northern part of the Ob gulf (E) is of convergent nature. The gulf is shallower in its eastern side. So the core of the fresh water shifts to the eastern shore of the gulf. This in turn results in east-to-west slope of isohalins and hence surfaces of equal density. This is documented in the field campaigns data. This slope should finally entail the slope of free surface and induce surface current from the eastern side of the gulf to its center, forming the convergence there. This front separating warm waters on the east and cold ones on the west is also visible on AVHRR images (though for different from the SAR images dates). The front itself appears in the visible channel as thin strip of more turbid water, probably due to litter accumulation. The several features marked with (F) we believe are fronts between fresh waters of river Pyasina runoff and sea waters. Little is known about usual position of these fronts and available in situ data are too sparse to support or disprove this hypothesis. So we tried to retrieve the current profile across the front using computer modeling.

We generated several gradually changing current profiles (see "trial current profiles" on figure 7) and put them to the input of EOM model along with other appropriate environmental and radar parameters for the selected segment of the front, see picture. The output of the model were than compared with real radar cross section profile extracted from the SAR image. Simulated RCS profile #2 seems to mimic the real one better than others. So we may conclude that current profile across the front looks like trial current profile #2 - mostly convergence with slight cyclonic shear. This support our hypothesis about the front origin because it is strong convergence that characterize fronts of presumptive type. Of course, such a reasoning is not a proof since EOM is known to be not perfect, the comparison is made qualitatively and the convergence may be resulted from other causes.

Figure 7. Study of one SAR ocean front (upper left image), its backscatter profile (middle left figure), modelled current profiles across the front (lower left fig) and various simulated backscatter profiles using the EOM model.

The rest of the marked front-like features can not be interpreted reliably because of absence of auxiliary information. The so random distribution of the fronts is quite surprising for us. The spreading of the river water in Kara sea as usually given in the literature shows that the maximum salinity gradients lie in the exit of Ob gulf and between Sibiryakova island and main land. So these are areas where fronts are expected to appear most often. During KAREX-94 campaign a very sharp front accompanied by litter strip and changing water color was indeed observed visually to the east of Sibiryakova island. However the fronts detected in this study do not seem to concentrate in the mentioned regions. Moreover fronts caused by Ob and Yenisey outflow do not follow the pattern expected for the fronts bounding a spot of fresh waters lying on ambient sea water - more or less closed line around the rivers mouths. At the same time fronts of Pyasina outflow (which is 15 times less then total one of Ob and Yenisey) do follow the pattern. The front of Rhine river (which outflow is even more less) described by Vogelzang at el. follows the pattern too. So the conclusion may be that as the outflow increases the portion of current fronts caused by salinity ones decreases.

6.5 SAR interactions with sea ice

This study, which is the Dr. Sc. thesis of Jostein Solhaug, has been divided into 3 different approaches to the problem of microwave backscatter from sea ice in general, and SAR backscatter in particular. The Geophysical part includes in situ measurements and media modelling. The Electromagnetic part includes an exact scattering model of microwave pulses in various modelled media. And the SAR part includes discussion and demonstration of the predicted results as a tool to better interpret SAR data of sea ice.

Geophysical part.

In order to model backscatter from sea ice, the micro structure of the ice crystals, air bubbles and the brine in the ice has to be fully understood. Field measurements of density-, salinity-, and temperature- profile in core samples of sea ice has been made during several cruises in the Barents Sea and Fram Strait. It has been focused on understanding the time evolution of sea ice as it is formed and deformed under various environmental conditions with special focus on sea ice in Norwegian arctic waters. The study of air/sea/ice interactions were mostly carried out during a 6 month visit at UNIS in Longyearbyen, and in the three field cruises around Spitsbergen.

Field measurements.

During the field campaigns, SAR data was processed at NERSC and sent to the ships by fax a few hours after the satellite over-pass. These SAR images were used to plan the in situ measurements sites. At the sites, several full length cores of the sea ice were drilled. The temperature gradient and volume of the cores were measured on site before they were transported on board the ship. There the volume, weight, and salinity were measured for all cores. These profiles show the

characteristics of sea ice reported by others for first year ice at different stages of development, but unfortunately, the sensitivity of the available sensors did not give the expected consistency of ice type and profiles, and the profiles are subject to further analysis. The environmental and large scale ice conditions were also documented. These cruises did demonstrate the use of 'almost real-time' SAR data in ship navigation in icy waters, and important experience in interpretation of SAR data is being tuned for future SAR data interpretations.

Electromagnetic part.

The remote sensing signal:

In order to utilise the available SAR data from ERS, Radarsat and from the planned Envisat mission, the SAR backscatter has to be explained from an electromagnetic point of view. The signal transmitted from the SAR is a vertical or horizontal linear polarised coherent microwave pulse at wavelengths in X, C or L-band, and hits the geoid with an fixed angle of incident. The models assume that the signal is not affected by atmospheric absorption or scattering, and is known at the air/ice interface. The signal is then scattered back to the SAR where either the vertical or horizontal polarised component of the electromagnetic pulse is received at the SAR antenna and sent to a ground station for image processing.

Since the planned Envisat mission will transmit and measure in both V and H polarisation, the SAR signal from the receiving antenna will include the complete polarisation matrix (VV, HH, VH, and HV) and where the cross polarisation parts (HV and VH) are of particular interest.

The backscatter:

The transmitted pulse is scattered by the sea ice in two separate mechanisms. The surface reflection is determined by the roughness and geometry of the air/ice or air/snow interface, and is the dominant mechanism to the VV and VH backscattered signal from ice covered with wet snow or melt ponds. The volume scattering is the dominant part of the signal from low-saline multi-year ice covered with none or dry snow. It is believed that the geometry of the brine pockets in the ice are of crucial importance for the cross polarisation.

The backscatter models:

A Polarimetric Radiative Transfer (PRT) model is under development with various sea-ice-model media. This model has recently been implemented at the Geophysical Institute, Fairbanks, Alaska by the atmospheric group lead by Prof. Knut Stamnes, for studies of optical Mie and Rayleigh scattering in the atmosphere. By defining the elliptic geometry of the scattering particles in accordance to the observed brine pocket sizes in sea ice, this model can be used with various boundary conditions. Also multiple layers of inhomogeneous anisotropic media will be implemented.

Teaching, field experiments and visits abroad.

May 1996: Participant of cruise with 'RV Jan Mayen' in the Barents Sea.

Aug 1996: Participant of cruise with 'RV Jan Mayen' in the Barents Sea.

Spring 1997: in situ measurements on Spitsbergen and in the Fram Strait during 6 months visit at UNIS.

Spring 1997: Teaching field course AGF215 at UNIS.

7-19 Sep 1997: Participant of NATO ASI on Ice Physics in the Natural and endangered Environment, Acquafredda di Maratea, Italy.
Spring 1998: Teaching 'SOT540: Miljøovervåkning' at HIB.
May 1998: Teaching and supervising field course AGF215 at UNIS.
May 1998: Supervising cruise with 'RV Polarsyssel' in Fram Strait.
Aug 1998: Participant of IGARSS' 98, Seattle, USA.
Aug-Oct 1998: Guest at Geophysical Inst., Univ. of Alaska, Fairbanks.

7. Other projects supporting development of SAR applications

GIS / MIS

The Nansen Center is developing GIS systems for the marine environment, called Marine Information System (MIS), which can incorporate various types of remote sensing data, in situ data and model data (Hamre, 1995; Jacob, 1995; Jacob and Hamre, 1998). Further development of SAR algorithms and other analysis methods will be integrated into a MIS at the Nansen Center. Both Hamre's Dr. Scient fellowship (completed 1995) and Jacob's Dr. Scient fellowship (1997 - 1999) are supported by the Norwegian Research Council.

Ocean surface processes

The Nansen Center is performing a project entitled "Studies of surface processes influencing climate" financed by the Norwegian Research Council where one of the highlights so far is a global survey of the coverage of the ocean by natural surface films, using the SIR-C/X radar on the NASA space shuttle. These films, composed of surfactants generated by biological processes, tend to restrict air-sea gas and energy exchange. A report has been prepared (Bresciano & Jenkins, 1998, NFR report in press) which indicates that the global coverage, though small, does tend to be concentrated in coastal waters, where biological activity is high, so that their effect on biologically-related gas exchange etc. may be significant. Work is in progress to quantify this effect, using an ocean-basin-scale marine ecological numerical model. Two papers have been published, relating the dynamics of the above types of surface film, and their damping effect on surface capillary waves, to conventional viscous parameters of films of finite thickness (Jenkins & Dysthe, 1997; Jenkins & Jacobs, 1997). The effect of a breaking wave crest in generating a turbulent plume has been quantified, together with its effect in mixing down passive tracers into the water column. The absolute scale size of this phenomenon is now under investigation, by an analytical study of periodic breaking waves. An alternative, more computationally expensive, Volume of Fluid model for wave breaking, has also been successfully installed on the Origin 2000 computer in Bergen, in collaboration with IRPHE in Marseille, so it may be possible to compare the theoretical results obtained with detailed numerical computations.

Eastern Programme

The Norwegian Research Council is supporting a Nansen Fellowship Programme in Russia where 2 Ph. D. students are working with marine applications: D. Akimov is working with SAR ocean simulation models and A. Bogdanov is working with SAR ice classification. The results of these studies will be integrated into our new proposal.

ESA projects

The Nansen Center has been the project leader of two studies for ESA which have investigated use of SAR and other satellite sensors in marine monitoring. The studies are entitled “Synergetic use of infrared, optical and microwave remote sensing observation” (Miles et al., 1998) and “Intercomparison and improvement of SAR ocean imaging interaction models” (Jenkins et al., 1998). The two reports provide the most recent and up-to-date discussion of the role of SAR in ocean and ice observation and the state-of-the-art of current SAR algorithms. The Nansen Center has also produced two SAR application catalogues for ESA, for promotion of SAR in coastal and sea ice monitoring: a SAR Ocean Feature Catalogue (Johannessen et al., 1994) and an ERS SAR Ice Catalogue (Johannessen et al., 1997d).

EU projects

PROMISE (Pre-Operational Modelling In the Seas of Europe) is testing and improving ocean models for use in ocean monitoring and forecasting. Provision of data sets, including satellite data, which can be used in the models is an essential part of the project. The Nansen Center, which is partner in the project, is studying the role of remote sensing applied to operational models (Jenkins et al., 1997a). PROMISE is funded under CEC MAST III.

COASTMON (Metocean and coastal zone monitoring in harbor regions using satellite radar) is exploring and testing methods for use of SAR and other new satellite sensors in monitoring environmental conditions (wind, waves, currents) in coastal areas. The study is performed in co-operation with end users who need to access to improved metocean data. In Norway, Fedje Coastal Station is one of the key users of metocean data for ship traffic management in the Mongstad area where many large tankers operates every day. The Nansen Center, which is coordinator (A. Jenkins) of this project, is demonstrating SAR wind products, SAR front and eddy features, SAR wave spectra and other satellite data products to a selection of key users (Jenkins et al., 1997b). COASTMON is funded under CEC Climate and Environment Programme (CEO).

The Nansen Center is coordinator and participant in several satellite ice monitoring demonstration projects funded by EU which utilizes SAR ice classification methods developed by scientists at the Nansen Center. The projects are summarized in table 1:

Table 1. Over view of satellite ice projects funded by EU

Project acronym	Full project title	EU programme	Role of Nansen Center	Project period
OSIMS	Operational Sea Ice Monitoring in Europe	DG12 Env. & Climate	coordinator S. Sandven	1996 - 1998
IMSI	Integrated use of new Microwave Satellite data for improved sea Ice observation	DG12 Env. & Climate / CEO	coordinator S. Sandven	1997 - 1999
ICE ROUTE	Application of advanced technologies to the routing of ships trough sea ice	DG 7: Transport	partner	1997 - 1998
ARCDEV	Arctic Demonstration and Exploration Voyage	DG 7: Transport	partner	1998 - 1999
ICE STATE	Local Ice Cover Deformation and Mesoscale Dynamics	DG12 MAST III	partner	1996 - 1999

Other spinoff projects

Norwegian Space Centre and ESA have supported demonstration projects at the Nansen center showing how SAR data can be used in operational monitoring of currents, fronts, eddies, slicks and oil spills in Norwegian waters (Samuel et al., 1995; Sandven et al., 1997). Norske Shell oil company is using satellite data (altimeter, SAR and AVHRR data) to investigate currents, eddies and fronts as preparation to deep sea drilling off the continental shelf of Mid-Norway (Haugen et al., 1998).

The Nansen Center has established use of SAR data to map sea ice in the area north of Svalbard. After the accident with "Atlantic Prawn" which sunk in sea ice in December 1995, it is recognized that the quality of the Norwegian ice charts in the Svalbard region is too poor. It is now planned to establish a Norwegian Ice Service at DNMI in Tromsø where the Nansen Center will provide SAR ice classification products.

The Nansen Center, in cooperation with the Terra Orbit A/S which is a commercial company in the Nansen Group, is now providing commercial service to oil companies and shipping companies, especially in the Northern Sea Route.

Terra Orbit A/S together with Storm Weather A/S, a TV2 company, and the Nansen Center have provided ice cover maps of the Norwegian, Greenland and Barents Seas from passive microwave satellite data (SSM/I) every Monday on TV-2's regular weather forecast. This is the first time in the world that satellite ice cover data has been shown on regular weather forecast on TV. The same group was also recently awarded a new ESA Announcement of Opportunity ("AO") project where detailed SAR ice information from Svalbard and Barents Sea will be shown on TV-2's weather forecast, demonstrating the usefulness of SAR ice monitoring for ship traffic and fishing vessels in polar regions. This is today feasible because almost every vessel can receive TV onboard.

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